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New Energy Possibilities

The Grassroots push for a new energy raises questions that have been around for a long time. Taking a cue from some of the web sites on this subject we can find a solution.

The clue is Godel's theorem, which states that we have only models and incomplete ones at that. I believe the Gods would agree with that, having given us initiation centers or mystery schools of old to educate who they could about spiritual concepts. We have to address the inertia of these new concepts that seems to consume almost all who have come before us. First, we must abandon the concept that this zero point energy is just a mechanical type thing, a sort of force. It is the trapings of the Gods themselves. For proof of this, one can look at Klingsor, a black magician, who defeated almost everyone who came up against him, even the budding Christians. Klingsor knew of and had contact with cosmic powers, even if they were on the dark side. These dark cosmic powers protected Klingsor. Today, these Klingsor types are deep in policy making and will consume all who come up against them. The question of consciousness or new energy first is answered by Steiner in his Light Course, where the progressive Gods tried via electricity to raise the consciousness of man and were not successful. So today, we have to raise our consciousness first and the energy will come from that. This, I believe the Gods will support.

To believe that this new energy is safer than present methods is a false notion. If the terrorists get a hold of it in a small form then it is no different than a suitcase nuke or anthrax. So to be successful, we must first make contact with the cosmic powers via Long's high self magic. We must abandon the notion of waves and so-called free energy. The progressive Gods gave us life for free; I do not believe they will give us this for free without a battle. Certainly, even the dark cosmic powers will fight this, but if my theory is correct, they will be defeated.

*Tom Batorski
Angola, NY*

Ziggurat or Hill

Your credibility will not be enhanced when you mix up your illustration material.

While some of your readers perhaps accept the steep hill you show (#41, Sept./Oct. 2003, p. 28) as being "the ruins of the ancient ziggurat of Dur Kurigatzu," any geologist will need just a few seconds of 'remote viewing' to classify it as an ordinary sedimentary sequence, possibly sandstone, moulded by erosion.

*Dr. J.B. Kloosterman (geologist)
Amsterdam, The Netherlands*

We apologize to Dr. Kloosterman, not for the accuracy of our caption, but for the quality of the printed image. If it had been printed more clearly, anyone, including Dr. Kloosterman, would have been able to see, despite the significant erosion noted, a number of obviously artificial features on the structure including windows and doorways. The well-known site approaches 170 feet in height and is, geological opinion aside, believed by most archaeologists to have been built in the 14th century B.C.
ED.

Research Dilemmas

What should a young researcher do when he thinks that he has a very important theory but his professor does not allow him to publish?

I was in this situation and still suffer

from it.

While writing my diploma thesis at the University of Bonn I developed a model of Dirac magnetic monopoles which predicts that electromagnetic radiation consists of two kinds of particles, Einstein's "electric photon" and Salam's "magnetic photon." I suggested a tabletop experiment to verify the "magnetic photon rays."

I planned to include my model in my diploma thesis. However, no professor at the university wanted to act as the second examiner as long as this model was part of my thesis. I removed my model from my thesis and got my diploma in physics in November 1995. By then I had published four articles in scientific journals.

Because of my model I was regarded as a crackpot in Bonn. I was unable to start a PhD thesis there. In April 1996 I started my PhD thesis at the University of Wuppertal.

I published my model in December 1997. I found that the duality between electricity and magnetism is analogous to the duality between curvature and torsion. I published an article on this finding.

My professor in Wuppertal was very unhappy about the publication of my model. He declined to accept my PhD thesis.

I am very grateful to the staff of the physical institute of the University of Dortmund who offered me a position to complete my PhD thesis. It was accepted in July 2001. By then I had published ten articles in scientific physical journals. However, after completion of my PhD thesis I remained unemployed.

I learned that August Kundt in 1885 may have already observed the magnetic photon rays I predicted. I published a paper on this interpretation.

I contacted several experimentalists whether they would like to test my prediction of the magnetic photon rays. My interpretation of the Kundt experiment was of great help to convince two independent researchers to perform the suggested tabletop experiment.

The first experiment was tried in Austria in February 2002 and the second experiment in the USA in June 2002. Both experiments showed a signal which was very difficult to explain without the introduction of magnetic photons. However, the signal was 1000 and 6000 times, respectively, smaller than I predicted in my publication.

The experimentalists were not convinced

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that they have proved my theory. So they have not published their results. Further experiments have not been performed. What should I do? I decided to publish their experiments including my interpretation of their results. The two experimentalists agreed with this way of publishing provided I included a statement that they strongly disagree with my interpretation of their results. The paper includes this statement and will be published as a contribution to a book.

To conclude, what can happen when a young researcher thinks he has an important theory? From my own experience I learned that he will get difficulties with the acceptance of his diploma thesis. It will become impossible to start a PhD thesis at the same university. His professor will decline to accept his dissertation. After completion of his PhD thesis he will be unemployed, although by then he has ten scientific publications, eight of them authored by him alone.

*Rainer W. Kühne
Wuppertal, Germany
Atlantis Rising Forums*

Ancient Engineering

A while back I was watching a program about Machu Pichu on TV. It was interesting and informative until they came to the part about how the builders cut the stones for the walls and buildings. They said it was done by hammering one rock against another, in this case granite. They had just shown a section of a wall that was made of identically sized rectangular stones with ruler-straight courses and seams. It was made up of hundreds of stones. I thought, let's see, the boss of the work party brings his gang to a huge pile of granite boulders and says, Okay, guys, I want two hundred blocks cut out of this granite, each one precisely 12x2x18 inches (or whatever). All angles to be 90 degrees, all edges sharp. Here are your tools. He hands them a bunch of rocks.

Archaeologists apparently believe this nonsense and expect us to as well. There had to be another way.

When Uri Geller and others bend a spoon or fork with their mind, the metal softens but does not melt. If it melted there would be some burnt fingers. Could it be that the megalithic builders had a way to soften stone temporarily so that it could easily be cut? It would explain how they got those odd shaped blocks to fit together.

*William R. Bailey
Gig Harbor, WA*

If the Egyptians or their ancestors (alien colonists) built the pyramids, why then was not the knowledge of how the construction of the pyramids were accomplished not

pasted down from generation to generation? Why do they (Egyptians) not possess any knowledge of their historical past with respect to the actual building of the pyramids?

Why are not the Egyptians among the greatest mathematicians or builders in the world, that is (if) "the linear progression of technology" had actually occurred as academia has postulated?

I propose that the great stone buildings (forts) where actually fall-out shelters. I base this on the fact that we have on the ancient time line a sudden event of missing cultures described by the ancient Vedic Sanskrit. The Ramayana Mahabharata and other ancient text speak of a hideous war that took place ten to twelve thousand years ago between Atlantis and Rama using weapons of mass-destruction.

The ancient Mahabharata text, a source on Vimana air-ships, goes on to tell of the awesome destructiveness of the war:

A single projectile charged with all the power of the universe (Atom Bomb), an incandescent column of smoke and flame as bright as a thousand suns rose in all its splendor. The entire race of Vrishnis and Andhakas corpses so burned as to be unrecognizable. Hair and nails fell out. To escape from the fire, soldiers threw themselves into the streams to wash themselves and their equipment.

These references are not isolated events. For instance, the skeleton remains excavated in the Rishi City of Mohenjodaro were found to be among the most radioactive ever found even on a par with those at Hiroshima and Nagasaki. Archaeologists found skeletal remains just lying in the streets, holding hands as if some overwhelming catastrophe suddenly overtook them. The massive stone buildings and forts vitrified from the intense heat of the blast! Vitrified buildings can be found in France, Turkey, India Scotland, Ireland and other places around the globe.

Black lumps of glass, discovered at Mohenjo-Daro, a well planned city laid out on a grid, with plumbing systems superior to those used in Pakistan and India to this day, were discovered to be clay pots that had melted under intense heat! After the devastation the world collapsed into a stone-age of sorts and modern man's history picks up from there a few thousand years later.

Why then does it not seem surprising that enlightened human beings would have preserved advanced technology by encoding it into their artifacts knowing full well that one day it would be rediscovered?

*TSM
Reverse Engineering Specialist
Atlantis Rising Forums*

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